

STUDY ON CHEMICAL TREATMENT OF CELLULOSE FIBER TO IMPROVE HEAT RESISTANCE AND THE MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS USING TREATED FIBER

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1 Introduction

In recent years, the issues of global warming and environmental load reduction have been attached great importance to science and industry. For fiber-reinforced plastics used for the structure material of car and home appliances, the environmental load reduction by using natural materials attracts attention. In this trend, various type of green composite, which consists of cellulose fiber reinforcements and thermoplastic resin matrix, are devised [1]. However, the hydroxyl groups of the cellulose macromolecule readily decompose, releasing water molecules by heating, which result in the heat degradation of the cellulose fibers. Therefore, cellulose fibers often discolor and stink during melting of the resin during molding process of the green composite. Consequently, the mechanical properties of the composite cannot be as anticipated in many cases. In this study, methods for improving the heat resistance property of cellulose by making cellulose fiber react to organosilicon compounds has been proposed, in which siloxane bonds (Si-O) are formed with the hydroxyl groups on the surface of cellulose fiber. In addition, the heat deterioration of treated cellulose fiber was evaluated. Furthermore, with the above-mentioned technique, the fiber reinforced composite materials were

prepared using the heat-resistant cellulose and the mechanical properties were examined.

2 Experiments

2.1 Material and Heat Resistance Treatment

In this research, due to its widespread industrial use, cotton fiber (*Gossypium hirsutum L.*) was selected as the source of the cellulose fiber. The average fiber length and diameter were 27.1 mm and 19.5 μm , respectively. The untreated cellulose fiber is noted as "raw cellulose".

Tetraethoxysilane (TEOS) was selected to form siloxane bondings on the surface of the cellulose fiber. Hydrochloric acid and *n*-hexane were used as a reaction catalyst and dispersion medium, respectively.

The heat resistant treatment method is described below. Firstly, cotton fiber web was weighed and was immersed in *n*-hexane (1:20 fiber to *n*-hexane by weight). Next, a reaction liquid that consists of TEOS and 7 molar equivalent of 0.1 M HCl_{aq} was prepared. The "TEOS weight fraction" is defined as the value of (TEOS weight) / (cellulose weight) in the reaction. The reaction liquid was added to the cellulose-containing *n*-hexane with the range of TEOS weight ratio between 0.69 and 69.4. The reaction mixture was stirred with a stirring rod for 1

hour, then the treated cellulose was washed and neutralized by 0.1 M Na₂CO₃ solution. The product was dried in a drier at 105 °C for 24 hours. The heat resistant cellulose fiber was obtained thereby. The cellulose fiber after the treatment is noted as “heat-resistant cellulose”.

As the matrix resin of the fiber reinforced composite material, polypropylene, which is commodity plastic and has relatively low melting point, was selected. To mix the matrix with the cellulose fiber uniformly, fibrous polypropylene (noted as “PP fiber”) was used. PP fiber was purchased from Daiwabo Polytec Co, Ltd. (PZ, the fiber fineness is 6.7 dtex, with fiber length of 64 mm).

2.2 Molding Method of Fiber Reinforced Composite Material

The heat-resistant cellulose fibers or the raw cellulose fibers were uniformly mixed with the PP fibers with a carding machine. Fig.1. shows the photo of carding machine. Next, the mixed fiber web preform was put into a heated metal mold. The composite materials were formed by compression molding with the molding pressure of 3.12 MPa, the heating temperatures of 170, 180, 200, 220 °C and the heating time of 5, 15, 30 and 60 minutes. Scheme of compression molding is shown in Fig.2.

2.3 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) Observation

The surface morphology of the cellulose fiber appears to exert a large influence on the formability of the composite material. Therefore, the fiber surfaces before and after the heat-resistant treatments were observed by SEM (S-3000, Hitachi Ltd.).

The strength of the fiber reinforced composite largely depends on the adhesiveness between the cellulose fiber and the resin. Then, the fractural cross section of the fiber reinforced composite for the tensile test was also observed by SEM (S-3000, Hitachi Ltd.).

2.4 X-Ray Photoelectron Spectrometry (XPS)

To determine whether the elemental composition of the cellulose fiber changed before and after treatment, the elemental content of the sample was

Fig.1. Carding machine

Fig.2. Scheme of compression molding

measured by XPS (JPS-9010 MC/SP, JEOL). Mg K α ($h\nu=1253\text{eV}$) was used as the X-ray source.

2.5 Evaluation of Mechanical Properties

2.5.1 Tensile Test of Single Fiber

The tensile test of the single fiber was based on JIS L 1069 and carried out using a universal testing instrument (Autograph AGS-J, Shimadzu. Co). The span length and test speed were 10 mm and 20 mm/min, respectively.

The heat resistance of the single cellulose fibers was evaluated by measuring the tensile strength of the single fiber of raw cellulose and heat-resistant cellulose after 5-30 minutes exposure to 170-240 °C and returning to room temperature.

2.5.2 Tensile Test of Fiber Reinforced Composite Material

By the tensile test of the cellulose fiber reinforced composite, the effect of heat-resistant treatment for the cellulose fiber on the tensile strength of the fiber reinforced composite material was investigated. The tensile test was based on JIS K 7113 and carried out using Autograph AGS-J. The size of specimens was 100×10×1 mm. The span length and the test speed were 70 mm and 20 mm/min, respectively.

2.6 Inspection with Color Measurement

When cellulose deteriorates by heat, discoloration occurs. Therefore the discoloration of the fiber and the composite material by heat was measured. Based on JIS Z 8729, colorimetry was performed using a spectrum colorimeter (CM-3600d, Konica Minolta, Inc). The L*a*b* color system is most widely used for the measurement of the color difference in the field of the industrial color management. The chromatic aberration value (ΔE^*_{ab}) was determined for each specimen. ΔE^*_{ab} is defined as the equation (1), here ΔL^* , Δa^* , Δb^* are differences in lightness, chroma and hue calculated from L*a*b* coordinates, respectively.

$$\Delta E^*_{ab} = [(\Delta L^*)^2 + (\Delta a^*)^2 + (\Delta b^*)^2]^{1/2} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

2.6.1 Color Measurement of Fiber

The deterioration of the raw cellulose fiber and the heat-resistant cellulose fiber were evaluated by measuring the chromatic aberration after 15 minutes exposure to 160-240 °C and returning to room temperature.

2.6.2 Color Measurement of Fiber Reinforced Composite Material

The fiber reinforced composite materials using raw cellulose fiber and heat-resistant cellulose fiber were evaluated by measuring the color difference of the composite materials after 5-60 minutes exposure to 170-220 °C and returning to room temperature.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Observation by SEM

Fig.3. SEM photograph of cellulose fiber before and after TEOS treatment

Fig.4. SEM photographs of fracture cross section of composite materials

3.1.1 Surface of Fiber

Surface images of samples before and after heat-resistant treatment are shown in Fig.3. The findings reveal that the surfaces of the samples before and after treatment were smooth, with no obvious differences in fiber diameter observed. It is thought that the quantity of treating agent adhering to the surface of the fibers is sufficiently small that any diameter increase is negligible.

3.1.2 Fracture Cross Section of Composite

When the fiber surface is modified by a chemical treatment or a compound coating, the interfacial

adhesion between the fiber and the matrix sometimes becomes weaker. In order to discuss the interface conditions, the fractural cross section of the fiber reinforced composite was observed by SEM. The SEM photograph is shown in Fig.4. From the figure, the gap between the reinforcement fiber and the matrix is smaller for heat-resistant cellulose fiber than for raw cellulose fiber. Therefore it can conclude that the heat-resistant treatment improves interfacial adhesion.

3.2 Surface Elemental Analysis by XPS

XPS spectra of a cellulose fiber obtained before and after the heat-resistant treatment are illustrated in Fig.5. Peaks are observed at 285 eV for C_{1s}, 533

Fig.5. XPS spectrum of cellulose fiber before and after TEOS treatment (a) Whole graph (b) Enlargement graph

eV for O_{1s}, 748 eV for O_{KLL} and 995 eV for C_{KLL}. Fig.5 (b) shows magnified data from 60 to 180 eV; two peaks were found in this region, at 99 eV for Si_{2p} and at 151 eV for Si_{2s} which confirms the introduction of Si after treatment by TEOS.

An SiO₂ content of 6.2% was calculated from the peak area. Considering the results, it seems that Si was introduced on the surface of the cellulose fiber even though there were no obvious changes on SEM images.

3.3 Tensile Strength

3.3.1 Tensile Strength of Single Fiber

Fig.6. shows the results of tensile test of the single raw cellulose fiber and the heat-resistant cellulose fiber (TEOS weight fraction of about 20) with heat load at the range between 160-240 °C and without heat load under the heating period of 15 minutes. The tensile strength in both fibers decreases with increasing temperature. In addition, the heat-resistant cellulose fiber shows higher tensile strength than that of the raw cellulose fiber under the equivalent load conditions,

It see which indicates that the heat-resistant cellulose fiber shows lower strength reduction under

Fig.6. Relationship between the heating temperature and the strength of fiber (heating time 15minute)

heat load. Therefore, it suggests that the heat resistant treatment for the cellulose fiber in this research, the hydroxyl groups on the surface of the cellulose fiber form siloxane bandings with TEOS and thereby, the heat deterioration of the cellulose macromolecules, that generally happened under heating, was suppressed and the strength reduction was lowered as a consequence.

3.3.2 Tensile Strength of Fiber Reinforced Composite

3.3.2.1 Effect of Molding Time on Tensile Strength

ms that the strength of the composite depends on the heat resistance property of reinforcement fiber under the equivalent molding conditions. Fig.7. shows the tensile strength of the composite under various molding time at the molding temperature of 180 °C and the fiber content of 40 wt%. As is shown in figure, the composite materials containing heat-resistant cellulose fiber shows higher tensile strength than that of the composite material containing raw cellulose fiber at each molding time. It indicates that the tensile strength is preserved better in the case of the heat-resistant cellulose fiber. Moreover, as for raw cellulose fiber reinforced composite, the strength at the heating time of 15 minutes shows the highest value. However the strength of the heat-resistant cellulose fiber reinforced composite shows the highest value at the heating time of 30 minutes. It can be seen that the strength of both composite materials decrease with the increasing molding time. On the other hand, the row cellulose fiber reinforced composite showed larger strength decrement by heating than that of the heat-resistant cellulose fiber reinforced composite. In the case of the raw cellulose fiber reinforced composite, the effect of the heat deterioration of reinforcement fiber became larger, and the tensile strength decreases in the case of over 15 minutes of heating time. Because of their good heat resistance property, it is possible to mold the composite longer

Fig.7. Relationship between the molding period and the strength of composites (content rate of fiber 40wt%, molding temperature 180 °C)

Fig.8. Relationship between molding period and strength of composites (content rate of fiber 20wt%, molding temperature 180 °C)

time with better resin impregnations with smaller deterioration of cellulose in the case of the heat-resistant cellulose fiber reinforced composite. Even over 30 minutes heating, the thermal degradation of heat-resistant cellulose fibers is smaller and the tensile strength of the composite is higher compared to the raw cellulose fiber reinforced composite material.

The relationship between the molding time and the tensile strength of the composite materials at the molding temperature of 180 °C and the fiber contents of 20 wt% are shown in Fig.8. Compared to Fig.7 the tensile strength decreased at every condition. Even though, heat-resistant cellulose fiber reinforced composite shows higher tensile strength than that of raw cellulose fiber. In addition, there is no peak of the tensile strength in Fig.8. It seems that at lower fiber content, the impregnation of the resin achieved less than 5 minutes, and the tensile strength of the composite decreases due to the thermal deterioration of the fibers over 5 minutes.

3.3.2.2 Effect of Molding Temperature on Tensile Strength

The relationship between the tensile strength of the composite and the molding temperature at molding time of 15 minutes and fiber content of 40 wt%, are shown in Fig.9. From the figure, the heat-resistant cellulose fiber reinforced composite shows higher tensile strength than that of the raw cellulose fiber at every temperature. The tensile strength shows maximum value at the molding temperature of 180 °C. The difference between the tensile strength of both composites becomes larger with the increase of temperature over 180 °C. It seems that the heat-resistant cellulose fiber suppresses the strength decrement from heat load during composite molding. Moreover, it seems that the impregnation of the resin is insufficient due to low molding temperature as a reason for low tensile strength of the composite at the molding temperature of 170 °C.

3.4 Evaluation of Heat Resistance by Discoloration Measurement

Polymer degradation sometimes causes the discoloration of material. The discoloration of polymer occurs by polymer structure deformations. When the thermal decomposition of polymer occurs, conjugated double bondings are formed. Thereby the absorbance of visible light increases and the color of materials darken. Furthermore heating causes the formation of tar-like substance and the color changes to brown or black. Therefore, the heat resistance of the material can be evaluated by the measurement of the color change degree of the material after heating.

3.4.1 Evaluation of Discoloration of Cellulose Fibers by Heating

Fig.10 shows the relationship between the heating temperature and the chromatic aberration, ΔE^*_{ab} , of the fibers with the heating period of 15 minutes. From the figure, the chromatic aberration of heat-resistance cellulose fiber is smaller than that of the raw cellulose fiber. It seems that the raw cellulose fiber forms the conjugate double bonding by heating. On the other hand, since the heat-resistant cellulose fiber has already formed siloxane bondings, the decomposition of hydroxyl groups and the formation of conjugated double bondings are suppressed.

3.4.2 Evaluation of Discoloration of Composites by Heating

Fig.11 shows the relationship between the molding time and the chromatic aberration, ΔE^*_{ab} , of the composite for the molding temperature of 180 °C. Also Fig.12 shows the relationships between the molding temperature and the chromatic aberration, ΔE^*_{ab} , of the composite for the molding time of 15 minutes. From the figures, the chromatic aberration of the heat-resistant cellulose fiber reinforced composite material is smaller than that of the raw cellulose fiber reinforced composite material. It indicates that the discoloration of the reinforcement

fiber results the discoloration of the composite itself when the transparent resin such as PP is used as a matrix. In comparison with Fig.12 and Fig.10,

Fig.9. Relationship between molding temperature and strength of composites (content rate of fiber 40wt%, molding period 15 minute)

Fig.10. Relationship between heating temperature and chromatic aberration of fiber (heating period 15 minute)

Fig.11. Relationship between heating time and chromatic aberration of composite material (molding temperature 180 °C)

Fig.12. Relationship between molding temperature and chromatic aberration of composite material (molding time 15minute)

ΔE^*ab of the composite material is similar to that of the fiber itself. Since the discoloration of pure PP board is 1.84 under equivalent conditions, there may be a little effect of discoloration of PP resin on the discoloration of the composite. In addition, since the cellulose fiber discolored even when the fibers were embedded in PP resin, the discoloration may not depend on oxygen in the atmosphere and the structure of cellulose polymer changes by itself. From these results, it is clarified that the discoloration of the heat-resistant cellulose fiber reinforced composites is suppressed.

3.5 Relationship between tensile strength and discoloration

3.5.1 Tensile strength and discoloration of fiber

Fig.13 shows the relationship between the chromatic aberration, ΔE^*ab , and tensile strength of single fiber for the heating temperature of 160-240 °C and heating period of 15 minute. From the figure, when the chromatic aberration of raw and heat resistant cellulose fiber become larger, the tensile strength linearly decreases. Even at same chromatic aberration, the strength reduction of heat resistant cellulose is smaller than that of the raw cellulose. The heating of cellulose polymer generates conjugated double bondings in molecular structure, which may change the color of cellulose more dark, and the strength of fiber decreases. Due to the formation of siloxane bondings on heat resistant cellulose fiber, the color change resulting from the generation of conjugated double bondings and the strength reduction may be suppressed.

3.5.2 Tensile strength and discoloration of composites

Fig.14 shows the relationship between the chromatic aberration, ΔE^*ab , and the tensile strength of cellulose fiber reinforced composites for the molding temperature of 170-240 °C and molding time of 15 minute. For heat resistant cellulose fiber reinforced composite material, tensile strength takes maximum value at the chromatic aberration of 20.

When the chromatic aberration is larger than 20, the tensile strength decline. For raw cellulose fiber reinforced composite material, the tensile strength

Fig.13. Relationship between chromatic aberration and strength of cellulose fiber (heating period 15minute)

Fig.14. Relationship between chromatic aberration and strength of composite material (molding period 15minute)

takes maximum value at chromatic aberration of about 30. The strength reduction of the heat resistant cellulose fiber reinforced composite materials is smaller than raw cellulose fiber reinforced composite materials over 30 of the chromatic aberration. With chromatic aberration less than 20, because of the low heat load, PP fiber may not melt completely and PP impregnation to cellulose fiber is inadequate, the tensile strength of composite becomes lower. With increasing the heat load, the chromatic aberration becomes larger, at the same time, PP impregnation to cellulose fiber may improve, and thus the strength of the composite increases. With higher heat load due to significant degradation of cellulose fiber, the strength of the fiber itself decreases and therefore the strength of the composites also decreases regardless of impregnation improvement. For heat resistant cellulose fiber reinforced composites, due to the strength reduction of the fiber itself is smaller than raw cellulose fiber, the peak of tensile strength may shift to the region at higher chromatic aberration.

4 Conclusions

The decrement of the tensile strength of the cellulose fiber reinforced composite can be suppressed by using the cotton cellulose fiber with heat-resistant treatment with organosilicon compound. In addition, the heat-resistant cellulose fiber reinforced composite materials can reduce the discoloration according to the results of the evaluation of the discoloration caused by polymer deterioration. The method of the heat-resistant treatment used in this study is useful for the molding of the cellulose fiber reinforced composite.

References

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